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Placeholder Session title

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Empowering Users: How Base4NFDI supports training development for research infrastructure services

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Abstract

This presentation demonstrates how Base4NFDI enhances a user-centred and sustainable development of research data management (RDM) services by integrating a systematic approach to training and documentation. Material created in this process is presented to invite the reuse of the employed approach and guidelines.

Base4NFDI is a joint initiative of all NFDI (National Research Data Infrastructure) consortia in Germany that aims to develop, promote, and establish reliable basic services for improving research data management across disciplines.

While moving through three development stages - initialization, integration and “ramp up for operation”, services not only develop their technical service based on user requirements – they also plan and develop documentation and training in a user-centred approach.

Base4NFDI integrates training into the development process of each service through dedicated task forces. These teams, consisting of service members, Base4NFDI [service stewards](#) [1], who facilitate collaboration with future users across NFDI consortia, and a cross-service training manager, ensure user enablement is a core component from the start. Regular meetings focus on how training can help achieve service goals. The training manager provides targeted support, quality assurance, and shares best practices across services, connecting with national and international RDM training initiatives. Base4NFDI also develops reusable [guides](#) [2] for documentation, effective webinars, and more, benefiting teams without dedicated training resources in the NFDI and beyond.

Step one of each service's training creation process is developing service 'personas'. This approach fosters empathy, shifting the focus from technical functionality to a user-centered development process. Base4NFDI offers persona workshops to all service teams in initialization phase and has published a [self-service guide](#) [3] that can be reused by others. Once a service team develops personas, their learning needs can be evaluated. Teams gather information on high-level topics, previous knowledge, and group size, then cluster them into training target groups.

Step two is to get a clearer picture of the service training content. That means to define what is in scope and out of scope for the training, for example when it comes to previous

knowledge expected, to then [develop learning objectives](#) [4]. The objectives in the [RDM Learning goal matrix](#) [5] are used wherever possible.

Based on target group definitions and the list of learning objectives, decisions for learning material formats, expected quantity of training sessions and the reuse or creation of learning material can be made. This is often the final step before a service moves to integration phase. This systematic approach helps inform a realistic effort estimation for any training work packages.

During integration phase training material is curated and / or created, tested and delivered as per the services training concept. While services then progress to "ramp up for operation" phase the focus is on scalability across diverse target groups and the enablement and recruitment of trainers and ambassadors.

This presentation demonstrates how integrating training from the start enhances user-centered RDM services, making them more sustainable and scalable. It argues that this approach is valuable to be adopted in service and tool development, both nationally and internationally.

Keywords: training, personas, learning goals, Base4NFDI, OER, open educational resource, training concept, webinar,

Competing interests

The author declares that she has no competing interests.

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